

A Dimensional Approach to Canine Bark Analysis for Assistance Dog Signaling

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Abstract. Standard classification of canine vocalizations is infeasible for assistance dogs, where data is inherently sparse and ethically constrained. We reframe this problem as a continuous regression task within a two-dimensional arousal-valence space. Central to our approach is an adjusted Siamese Network trained not on binary similarity, but on the ordinal and numeric distance between input pairs. Trained on the public Emotional Canines dataset, our model reduces critical "turn-around" errors by up to 50% on the challenging valence dimension compared to a regression baseline. Qualitative validation on real-world dataset confirms the learned space is semantically meaningful, establishing a proof-of-concept for robustly analyzing canine bark under severe data limitations.

Keywords: Assistance Dogs · signaling · barking.

1 Introduction

Epilepsy is a common neurological disorder where seizures are often drug-resistant, impacting millions of people worldwide [1-4]. Assistance dogs have emerged as a promising aid, capable of detecting pre-ictal Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs) through olfaction [5, 6]. Evidence shows that even untrained dogs can spontaneously alert to seizures, while trained dogs can do so with high accuracy and significant warning times [7, 8]. Despite these benefits, the inherent stress of seizure events raises important animal welfare considerations, as adverse health effects in responding dogs have been reported [9].

A critical challenge in seizure assistance is the design of the dog's signaling behavior, which must balance reliability with animal welfare. While artificial signals like a trained "spinning" motion can be automatically detected [10], they may conflict with a dog's innate stress responses, such as staring or barking. Adhering to animal-computer interaction principles [11], this work investigates the feasibility of leveraging a natural vocalization, the attention-seeking bark, as a trained and automatically detectable alert.

While supervised bark classification is well-established, leveraging large public datasets [12-15], these data-intensive methods are infeasible for our application of training a model on a single assistance dog. The rigorous data collection and

annotation processes required, even for dimensional models [16], cannot be replicated for an individual animal due to severe practical and ethical constraints. Data for one dog is limited to a short collection period, during which it is ethically prohibited to artificially induce high-stress scenarios to elicit a full spectrum of bark types. This real-world context yields a scarce and incomplete dataset, fundamentally shifting our challenge from standard classification to developing a robust detection method that can operate under these data limitations.

To overcome the limitations of categorical classification, this paper reframes canine vocalization analysis as a regression task, proposing a novel framework to map barks onto a continuous, two-dimensional arousal-valence space from limited and ordinally-labeled data. Central to our approach is an adjusted Siamese Network. Unlike canonical Siamese architectures that learn a binary similarity metric, our model is optimized for regression using an ordinal and numeric distance objective, allowing it to explicitly model the ordered relationships within the data (e.g., 'High' > 'Medium' > 'Low'). This enables a more accurate and psychologically grounded dimensional representation than is possible with standard metric learning. We validate the utility of the proposed emotional space by projecting real-world canine barks from specific contexts onto the learned manifold. While not a comprehensive examination, this analysis serves as a proof-of-concept, demonstrating the framework's potential for identifying target signaling behaviors for applications such as seizure alerting.

2 Related Work

2.1 Categorization of Canine Bark

The predominant approach to categorizing canine vocalizations has been context-driven classification, where discrete labels are derived from controlled situational stimuli (e.g., 'Stranger,' 'Fight,' 'Play') [12, 13, 17]. This methodology, however, presents limitations in granularity and specificity. For instance, distinct contexts like 'Ball' and 'Food' can elicit acoustically similar barks, making the labels ambiguous [17], while the need for secondary emotionality scales ('Aggressiveness', 'Playfulness') underscores the insufficiency of the primary situational labels [13].

These limitations have motivated a shift towards the dimensional model of emotion, drawing from foundational work in animal psychology [18, 19, 16]. This model characterizes affective states by their position within a continuous two-dimensional arousal-valence space (Fig. 1), defined by arousal (intensity) and valence (hedonic value). While this dimensional concept has been proposed to guide a more nuanced annotation process, its application in prior machine learning work has not extended to direct, continuous prediction. This study therefore proposes a continuous regression approach to map canine vocalizations directly to a coordinate within this dimensional space.

Fig. 1. Two dimensional arousal-valence space

2.2 Feature Extraction and Classification Models in Canine Bark Analysis

The conventional machine learning pipeline for canine bark analysis comprises several stages: data acquisition, feature extraction, model training, and classification. A significant body of research has focused on applying this pipeline to classify barks based on context or demographic characteristics such as breed and age [12, 15, 16, 17, 20, 21].

For feature extraction in bioacoustics, representations that model perceptual hearing, such as the Mel spectrogram and Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs), have become the de facto standard, providing a compact and relevant representation of an audio signal's spectral properties [21]. These features (see Fig. 2) are well-suited as input for Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), which are widely used for their ability to learn hierarchical features by treating spectrograms as images [22]. As the primary objective of this work is to reformulate the task from discrete classification to continuous dimensional regression, we employ this standard and well-validated approach, utilizing spectrogram features as input to a foundational CNN structure.

Fig. 2. Visualization of the Waveform, Spectrogram, MFCC of a canine bark sample.

2.3 Siamese Neural Networks for Feature Space

The Siamese Neural Network is a class of architectures designed for metric learning, where the primary objective is to learn a meaningful, low-dimensional embedding space rather than perform direct classification [23]. By processing input pairs through identical, weight-sharing subnetworks (see Fig. 3), it learns a generalizable similarity function that pulls similar samples closer together while pushing dissimilar ones apart. This makes the architecture highly effective for tasks with limited data per class, such as one-shot image recognition [24], and aligns with the goal of finding a discriminative, clustering-friendly embedding space where proximity reflects semantic similarity [25].

Fig. 3. Regular Siamese network architecture.

However, the canonical Siamese architecture is optimized for a binary similarity objective (i.e., 'similar' vs. 'dissimilar'), which is insufficient for our task. Our framework relies on ordinal annotations for arousal and valence (e.g., 'High', 'Medium', 'Low'), where the directional relationship between labels is crucial. To address this, we introduce an adjusted Siamese Network to learn a continuous scalar value that preserves these ordinal constraints. We validate its efficacy in learning a continuous dimensional representation from sparsely-labeled, ordinal data.

3 Methodology and Materials

3.1 Two-Dimension Emotional Space

Inspired by the circumplex model of affect (see Fig. 1), our methodology is designed to project raw canine vocalizations onto a continuous two-dimensional emotional space defined by the orthogonal axes of arousal and valence. The proposed pipeline (see Fig. 4) begins with a feature extraction stage, where each bark audio segment is converted into a spectrogram-based feature representation. Subsequently, we employ two independently trained models to predict a continuous scalar value for each coordinate. The outputs of these two models are then combined to form a (valence, arousal) coordinate, which is projected onto the emotional space. This projection allows for a quantitative evaluation of the bark's relative emotional category based on its position within the quadrants of the circumplex model.

Fig. 4. Projection of audio to emotional space

3.2 Data Segmentation and Feature Extraction

The feature generation pipeline begins with segmenting raw audio recordings to isolate individual vocal events from silent intervals. To account for the emotionally heterogeneous nature of continuous recordings, we employ an energy-based method, extracting non-silent segments using a threshold of 20 dB below the peak amplitude. The resulting variable-length segments are subsequently normalized to a fixed size of 5120 samples, a length determined by the median segment duration in our dataset. Segments shorter than this length are symmetrically zero-padded, while longer ones are framed using a sliding window with 50% overlap (a stride of 2560 samples). Finally, a Mel spectrogram is computed for each fixed-length segment, serving as the input feature representation for our models.

3.3 Model and Evaluation

Model Architectures. As this work reframes the task from discrete classification to continuous regression, we establish a baseline and our proposed model accordingly. A standard CNN serves as our baseline model (see Fig. 5). It takes a Mel spectrogram as input and is trained to directly regress the continuous numerical value corresponding to an ordinal label. Our proposed model is an adaptation of the Siamese architecture (Fig. 3). It utilizes the same base CNN as its weight-sharing base network. However, its training objective is fundamentally altered. Instead of learning a binary similarity metric, the network is trained as a regressor to predict the ordered numeric distance between the two input samples. For instance, if 'Input 1' has a label of 'High' (1.0) and 'Input 2' has a label of 'Low' (-1.0), the network's target output is their numeric difference, $1.0 - (-1.0) = 2.0$.

Training Protocol. To facilitate the regression task, the ordinal labels for both arousal and valence were first standardized to a numeric scale: 'High'/'Positive' to 1.0, 'Medium'/'Neutral' to 0.0, and 'Low'/'Negative' to -1.0. To mitigate the risk of data leakage and performance inflation from acoustically similar, overlapping frames, the

train-test split was performed at the event level. This ensures that all segments derived from a single, continuous vocal event reside exclusively in either the training or the test set.

Fig. 5. Baseline CNN Architecture.

Evaluation Metrics. Given our focus on learning an ordinal-structured space, our evaluation employs two distinct metrics.

Accuracy. To provide a uniform comparison with traditional classification approaches, we report standard accuracy. The continuous regression outputs from our models are mapped back to their nearest categorical labels ('High'/'Positive', 'Medium'/'Neutral', 'Low'/'Negative') using decision boundaries learned from the distribution of regression values on the training set.

Turn-around Percentage (TAP). The primary goal is to learn an embedding that preserves ordinality. The most severe violation of this principle is a "turn-around" error, where a 'High' instance is predicted as 'Low' or vice-versa. We therefore introduce the Turn-around Percentage (TAP) as our key evaluation metric, defined as:

$$\text{TAP} = \frac{N(\text{High} \rightarrow \text{Low}) + N(\text{Low} \rightarrow \text{High})}{N(\text{Total High}) + N(\text{Total Low})} \quad (1)$$

This metric quantifies the proportion of extreme misclassifications, providing a direct measure of the model's ability to learn the correct directional structure of the feature space. A lower TAP indicates a more robust ordinal embedding.

Implementation Details. All data processing, model training, evaluation, and visualization were conducted within the Google Colab cloud environment. The implementation relied on standard Python libraries, primarily utilizing TensorFlow

and Keras for model development, Librosa for audio feature extraction, and Matplotlib/Seaborn for generating visualizations.

3.4 Datasets

To facilitate a comprehensive evaluation, this study utilizes two distinct datasets: a publicly available, dimensionally-annotated corpus for model training, and a private, real-world collection for validation.

Emotional Canines Dataset. For the primary task of learning the dimensional emotional space, we employ the Emotional Canines dataset [16]. This public corpus is the largest of its kind annotated for dimensional analysis, containing 1,400 bark sequences from Siberian Husky and Shiba Inu breeds. The dataset, recorded at a sample rate of 22.05 kHz, is pre-partitioned to prevent subject overlap, with a training set of 600 sequences and a test set of 100 sequences per breed. Each vocalization is annotated with continuous labels for arousal and valence, and the sequences vary in duration from 0.06 to 30.02 seconds (mean:1.50s, median: 0.96s). Its dimensional annotation scheme makes it uniquely suited for the regression-based task central to our study.

Real-world Canine Bark Dataset. For validation and to assess real-world applicability, we collected the Real-world Canine Bark Dataset, a private corpus containing over 454 hours of audio from seven domestic dogs. Data was captured non-intrusively via collar-attached miniature voice-activated recorders (e.g., STTWUNAKE, DizerLin) as single-channel (mono) audio at a 16 kHz sample rate with 16-bit depth. A key characteristic of this "in-the-wild" dataset, summarized in Table 2, is the inherent sparsity of vocalization events in a natural domestic environment. Across all subjects, the cumulative duration of identified bark events was 2183 seconds, accounting for merely 0.133% of the total recording time. This extreme class imbalance underscores the "in-the-wild" nature of the data and highlights the challenge of robustly detecting rare yet significant signaling behaviors, which is a central motivation for our proposed framework.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of the Real-World Canine Bark Dataset.

Dog Name	Recording Length (hh:mm:ss)	Bark Length (s)	Bark/Recording Ratio (%)
Bear	16:42:33	2	0.025
Bertie	8:10:50	11	0.336
Connie	37:23:51	6	0.108
Lexi	248:36:46	716	0.080
Mary	29:36:10	853	0.800
Rosie	65:18:55	311	0.132
Woody	49:05:05	44	0.025
In-All	454:54:10	2183	0.133

4 Results

4.1 Accuracy and Turn-Around Percentage

To quantitatively evaluate our approach, all models were trained and tested on the Emotional Canines dataset following the protocol outlined in Section 3. We establish multiple baselines for a comprehensive comparison. First, we cite the breed-specific classification accuracies originally reported in [16]. To provide a more direct comparison with our regression-based methods, we also trained a standard CNN classification model using the architecture from Fig. 5. Finally, both our proposed Adjusted Siamese Network and a baseline CNN Regressor were trained on the combined two-breed dataset to learn a generalized emotional space. The performance of all models on both the arousal and valence prediction tasks is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Performance comparison on the Emotional Canines test set. The results from [16] and our CNN (Classification) baseline are reported separately for the Husky and Shiba Inu breeds. The regression models were trained on the combined dataset.

Model	Arousal		Valence	
	Accuracy(%)	TAP(%)	Accuracy(%)	TAP(%)
Reported by [16]	42 / 46	-	34 / 45	-
CNN(Classification)	60.45 / 43.35	15.37 / 22.87	56.34 / 31.91	56.34 / 31.91
CNN(Regressor)	47.85	14.41	36.70	30.56
Adjusted Siamese	55.93	10.83	48.07	15.91

4.2 Visualization of Predicted Dimensional Distributions

To qualitatively assess how well each model learned the ordinal structure of the emotional space, we visualized the distribution of their continuous regression outputs on both the training and test sets. Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 illustrate the predicted value distributions for the arousal and valence dimensions, respectively, for both the baseline CNN and our proposed adjusted Siamese Network.

Fig. 6. Distribution of predicted arousal values for the baseline CNN (1) and adjusted Siamese Network (2) on the test(a) and train(b) sets.

As shown in Figure 6, both models learn to effectively separate the three arousal categories on the training set, mapping them to distinct regions along the axis. On the test set, this separation is less pronounced for both models, a finding consistent with expected generalization performance. The adjusted Siamese Network (Fig. 6 (2.a)) maintains a clearer ordinal separation compared to the baseline CNN (Fig. 6 (1.a)).

The distributions for the valence dimension, shown in Figure 7, reveal a more pronounced difference between the models. While the Adjusted Siamese Network (Fig. 7 (2.a)) again shows a clear, albeit overlapping, separation of the three categories on the test set, the Baseline CNN (Fig. 7 (1.a)) struggles significantly. The distributions for the valence categories for the baseline model largely collapse into a single mode on the test set, indicating a failure to generalize the ordinal structure for valence. This visual evidence supports the quantitative results, suggesting that the training objective of the adjusted Siamese Network makes it more capable of learning a robust, ordinally-structured embedding, particularly for the more challenging valence dimension.

Fig. 7. Distribution of predicted arousal values for the baseline CNN (1) and adjusted Siamese Network (2) on the test(a) and train(b) sets.

4.3 Real-World Canine Bark Dataset

To assess the generalizability of our model, we conducted a qualitative validation using the Real-world Canine Bark Dataset, a corpus characterized by the extreme sparsity of vocalization events (0.133% of >454 hours). This section presents a case study analysis, projecting specific, owner-identified bark events onto the emotional space learned from the curated dataset to evaluate the semantic validity of their resulting coordinates.

Following the protocol detailed in Section 3.2, the entirety of the 2183-seconds canine barks was segmented and processed to extract spectrogram features for all seven dogs. We then utilized our trained adjusted Siamese Network to predict the arousal and valence coordinates for each bark. The resulting projections, which map each real-world vocalization to a point in the learned emotional space, are visualized in Figure 8.

Fig. 8. Projection of barks from the seven dogs onto the learned arousal-valence space.

A qualitative analysis of these projections reveals a strong correspondence between the barks' positions in the learned space and the dogs' known behavioral contexts. For instance: a) Two distinct vocalizations from 'Woody', identified as soft snores during sleep, are projected as proximate points in the low-arousal, positive-valence quadrant (calm/relaxed), aligning with their passive context; b) In contrast, the majority of barks from 'Connie', a puppy known for frequent attention-seeking barks, are concentrated in the high-arousal, positive-valence quadrant, consistent with an excited or interested state. c) Conversely, vocalizations from 'Mary', who exhibits a strong tendency to bark at slight noises outside, are predominantly located in the high-arousal, negative-valence quadrant, which corresponds to an anxious or alarm state.

While the Real-world Canine Bark Dataset is inherently sparse and lacks precise ground-truth arousal and valence labels, this case-study analysis provides strong qualitative evidence for the validity of our learned emotional space. The consistent alignment between the predicted coordinates and the dogs' known behavioral characteristics suggests that our framework successfully generalizes from the curated training data to capture meaningful emotional information in a challenging, real-world setting.

5 Discussion

Reframing canine vocalization analysis as dimensional regression is a viable strategy that does not sacrifice accuracy but allows for a more ordinally coherent feature space, evidenced by the significantly lower Turn-around Percentage (TAP). Our Adjusted Siamese Network proved instrumental in learning a robust feature projection, particularly for the challenging valence dimension. Analysis of our private dataset confirmed the extreme sparsity of "in-the-wild" vocalizations, and while precise numerical validation on this data is infeasible, qualitative analysis suggests the learned emotional space is semantically meaningful and consistent with known behavioural contexts, providing a proof-of-concept for its generalization.

Despite these promising results, this study has limitations. We employed a foundational CNN with standard spectrograms, leaving the performance of more advanced architectures unexplored. The training was constrained by the Emotional Canines dataset, whose small scale and low benchmarks suggest inherent data ambiguity, limiting the performance ceiling of any model. Furthermore, our real-world validation was qualitative rather than a comprehensive, numerically-scored evaluation.

These limitations open avenues for future work. The learned space could be fine-tuned using larger, context-oriented datasets to anchor the coordinates to observable behaviours. Additionally, a detailed ablation study could disentangle the contributions of the base network architecture from the Siamese-style metric learning objective itself, leading to a more optimized framework for sparse, ordinally-annotated bioacoustics data.

6 Conclusion

This work successfully reframes canine vocalization analysis from classification to a continuous regression task, introducing an adjusted Siamese Network that learns a semantically coherent arousal-valence space from sparse, ordinal data. Our model outperforms baselines in preserving ordinal relationships, a critical requirement for meaningful dimensional embedding. Qualitative validation on a large, real-world dataset confirms the framework's generalizability. We provide a proof-of-concept for a methodology that moves beyond simple classification to enable a more nuanced, psychologically-grounded understanding of animal affect, laying the foundation for robustly detecting natural signaling behaviors in data-limited applications like seizure assistance.

Acknowledgments. This study was funded by Research Ireland (Grant Number: 22/FFP-P/11493), and by the Insight Research Ireland Centre for Data Analytics (Grant Number: SFI/12/RC/2289_P2).

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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